

Research Overview of College Quality Management under Quality Assurance Approach

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Abstract:

The objective of the article is to review research related to quality management of colleges and colleges of health in the direction of the approach quality assurance. From there, the author proposes issues that need to be studied in the future and offers solutions for quality management of medical colleges in accordance with the European approach to quality assurance of vocational education and training (EQAVET), in order to ensure and improve the quality of schools, aiming to meet the needs of the international labor market in the current context.

Keywords: Quality management of colleges, health, quality assurance

1. Introduction

The foundations of the Quality Management movement are considered to have originated in the early 1920s, and originated in industry, Dr. Walter A Shewhart (1891 – 1967), an American statistician, known as the father of statistical quality control, and the founder of the "Shewhart Cycle", or "Plan-Do-Test-Action" (PDCA). At the time, he worked at bell Telephone Company's laboratory in New York, involved in the production of millions of telephone relays, and he realized that post-event inspection was not a good way to ensure quality. He did research during the production process, monitoring to prevent items from being produced inappropriately. In 1924 he applied statistical methods to control product quality, invented the first modern control chart and demonstrated that variation in the production process leads to fluctuations in product quality. Shewhart's aim was to use statistical control to eliminate waste and procrastination. In 1931, he published the world's first book on quality control "Product Quality Economics Control" (Shewhart, 1980) and served as the basis for the teaching of Statistical Process Control today. [Graeme Knowles, p15]. In 1939, he wrote "Statistical Methods from the Point of View of Quality Control". In this book he first discusses the concept of problem solving. This concept eventually became the foundation for the cycle: Plan –do–check–act, the four-step process for quality improvement. This concept is commonly known as the Shewhart quality cycle. [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Walter_A._Shewhart]

Deming (1900-1993), was an American statistician who began to formulate his ideas in the 1930s, while researching methods for removing variability and waste from industrial processes. He began working at the Hawthorne Western Electric plant in Chicago, where Joseph Juran, a pioneering quality theorist, was a major American contributor to Japan's quality revolution. Meanwhile, he was introduced to Walter Shewhart, and was introduced by Walter Shewhart to some ideas about the development of the quality movement. Deming's initial contribution was to develop and improve Shewhart's methods – the 'plan, implement, test, act' (PDCA) cycle. Shewhart and Deming's statistical methods are now known as Statistical Process Control (SPC). [Edward Sallis]

The quality movement began to emerge after World War II, Japan was a heavily war-torn country, the first pioneer of the quality movement. Deming first visited Japan in the late 1940s, coming to work on the postwar census. In 1950 he was invited by Japan to give lectures to leading Japanese industrialists on the application of Statistical Process Control. Much of Japanese industry was destroyed by U.S. bombing raids, and what remained was mostly the production of poor-quality imitations of products in other countries. Deming makes the point that quality control should not begin. Instead, find out what their customers want and offer to design both manufacturing methods and products to the highest standards to meet customer expectations. He believes that his approach, if taken thoroughly, will help the average company become a market leader within about 5 years. [Edward Sallis]

The Japanese adopted the ideas of Deming, Joseph Juran and other U.S. quality experts who visited Japan at the time. The quality movement began to emerge in the manufacturing sector, followed by the service and banking industries. The Japanese developed the ideas of Juran and Deming and they called Total Quality Control (TQC), and used it to capture and create a large share of the world market for automobiles, electronics and consumer goods in the 1970s and 1980s. Much of this market dominance is the result of excessive attention to quality. The most famous pioneer of quality in Japan, Kauro Ishikawa, described the Japanese approach to China as 'the thinking revolution in management'. [Edward Sallis]

Even in their homeland, Deming and Juran's ideas have largely been ignored for years. In the 1950s and 1960s, U.S. businesses could sell everything they made in a world hungry for manufactured goods. The focus of the industrial production of the United States and most Western countries is to maximize output and profits, with no emphasis on quality. It wasn't until the late 1970s when many of their companies lost both market share and market share to the Japanese that some large American companies began to value the message of quality. They started asking why consumers preferred Japanese products.

Deming and Joseph Juran, along with other quality professionals, including Philip B Crosby and Armand V Feigenbaum gained traction in the United States and Western European countries in 1980, thanks to a nationwide NBC documentary called "If the Japanese make it, why don't we?" (If Japan Can, Why Can't We). The show highlights the dominance of Japanese industry in many U.S. markets. The latter part of the show features W Edwards Deming and his contributions to Japan's economic success. [Edward Sallis]

W Edwards Deming published his most important book, *Out of the Crisis*, in 1982. He wrote in response to the crisis he claimed that U.S. industry was facing, while Japanese products were of better quality, and that he himself improved Japanese industry. As in the preface, "it is not the work of reproducing or modifying ... It requires a whole new structure, from the foundation up." [Edward Sallis]

Deming found that the quality problem was mainly in management. This was an important realization because the mainstream view of the time was that quality problems were the fault of workers. Deming offered 14 well-known quality management guidelines, including management principles and insights into employee psychology. The 14 points are Deming's unique contribution to quality, to developing a culture of quality that emphasizes prevention over healing. [Edward Sallis]

Joseph Juran (1904 – 2008), was the main veteran pioneer of the quality revolution. He was more appreciated in Japan than in his native United States. Juran published several books, the first of which was in 1951 with "Juran's Quality Control Handbook"; the book "Juran on Planning for Quality" was published in 1988, and "Juran on Leadership for Quality", published in 1989. He is famous for his phrase "fit for purpose". Juran was the first quality management expert to address quality management issues, and like Deming, most quality problems can be traced back to management decisions. He argues that poor quality is often the result of poor management. Using the Pareto principle (aka the 80/20 rule), Juran believes that 80% of an organization's quality problems are the result of manageable defects. Accordingly, 80% of the problems lie in management, and he argues that quality does not just happen, but it must be planned. [Edward Sallis]

Philip Crosby (1926 – 2001), known as "Quality is Free", served as quality director of the first Pershing missile program and later joined the International Telephone and Telegraph Corporation (ITT), serving as Corporate Vice President and Chief Quality Officer for 14 years. In 1979, Crosby published his most famous book, *Quality is Free*. He founded the Philip Crosby Association (Associates Incorporated) and the College of Quality in Florida, where he taught organizations how to manage and improve quality. In 1984, Crosby published "Quality Without Tears" as a connecting thread to other management books. Crosby's name is associated with two very charismatic and impactful ideas. The first is free quality. The second idea is the notion that errors, failures, waste, and delays—all 'shoddy stuff'—can be eliminated altogether if the organization intends to. He introduced the concept of quality as "zero defects", which is a controversial concept in thinking about quality and his main contribution. It is a powerful idea, committed to success and eliminating failure. It involves putting

systems in place to ensure that everything is always done right from the start and at all times. Crosby argues that the error-free goal, in a business context, will increase profits by saving costs. [Edward Sallis]

Tom Peters, his best-known book *In Search of Excellence* with Robert Waterman, published in 1982, examines the secrets of America's most successful institutions. *In Search of Excellence* is one of the most influential books on quality management. He analyzes the essential characteristics of excellence for the most competitive and profitable companies such as (a) close relationships with customers, (b) obsession and responsibility for quality, (c) simple and non-bureaucratic structures, and (d) rules that are based on active and enthusiastic teams. In his second book, *A Passion for Excellence*, with Nancy Austin, published in 1985, Peters identified leadership as the focus of the quality improvement process. More importantly, they argue that the term "management" should be removed in favor of "leadership." For them, the leader must be a facilitator and a visionary who motivates the rest of the team. In fact, they championed leadership style and characterized it with the well-known management by walking about (MBWA). Peters is best known for his customer-oriented views, and in *Thriving On Chaos* 1987, he describes 12 characteristics of the quality revolution that all organizations need to pursue. [Edward Sallis]

Kaoru Ishikawa (1915 – 1989), What is your most famous book "What is Total Quality Control"? The Japanese way (*What is Total Quality Control? The Japanese Way*), published in 1985. He is best known for his work on quality circles and was a pioneer of the Quality circle movement in Japan in the early 1960s. He is also famous for his statistical techniques, including herringbone or Ishikawa diagrams. A key feature of company-wide quality control in Japan is the quality circle. The quality circle is perhaps Japan's most famous contribution to quality management. The quality circle movement, which was connected to Ishikawa, began in 1962 at Nippon Telegraph and Telephone Public Corporation after which it spread to other countries and was exported worldwide. [Edward Sallis]

Barrie G. Dale (2003), with "Managing Quality," the fourth edition of the book, argues that the primary goal of quality assurance is to build quality for a product or service during upstream planning and design, give confidence to customers, products or services that work as they expect. Let everyone in the organization take personal responsibility for the quality of the learning processes undertaken.

Peter D. Mauch (2010) with "Quality Management: Theory and Application" pointed out the rationale in quality management such as organization, planning, control, human resources, motivation... According to the author management is a process or form of work that involves guiding or orienting a group of people to fulfill the goals, objectives or requirements of the organization. Quality management places an emphasis on planning. Quality control is a process for setting goals, monitoring performance and correcting errors for deviations; human resources, and motivation are indispensable components of quality management; propose a quality assurance system accountability matrix that includes level, organization, planning, control, team, and motivation[140]

Graeme Knowles (2011) in 'Quality Management' argues that if 'Quality' is the end point, then 'Quality Management' is the approach and process to get there. Lay out some of the key central principles of quality management practice. Point out that the traditional approach has many disadvantages compared to the quality management method, therefore it is necessary to implement quality management. On the other hand, to implement effective quality management, it is necessary to prioritize and implement strategic quality management, focusing on processes. At the same time, it points out indispensable factors in quality management such as: partnerships and resources, respect for each individual, motivation, empowerment, participation of people, creating a good working environment, teamwork, human development. Especially in quality management there is a need for process improvement, change and change management [Graeme Knowles]

Tim Landerville, President, Isocert Solutions, LLC (2014), "Quality Management Systems Guide", Quality management is not just an activity of the quality management department, it is a philosophy that is applied to

everyone in an organization, supported by the Executive Management Board and directed by the Quality Management department. In the 21st century, quality management systems (QMS) tend to converge with sustainability and transparency initiatives, both supplier and customer satisfaction, quality is increasingly associated with these factors. Implementing a quality management system is first of all determining the goals that the organization wants to achieve; next determine what others expect of the organization. The study lays out eight principles of quality management.

Syaiful Rizal HAMID, Saifuddin ISA , Boon Cheong CHEW and Abdullah ALTUN (2019), "Quality Management Evolution from the Past to Present: Challenges for Tomorrow" research indicates that Garvin (1988) has linked quality management eras to time series; i.e., from the Inspection Era to the eras of statistical quality control, quality assurance and finally strategic quality management. This article talks about the evolution and origins of quality management that can also be traced to the focus of quality over time. Researchers establish quality models — "focal points, principles, systems, and tools and techniques" over time. As the focus changes, so do the principles, and as the principles change, so do the systems, tools, and techniques in the field of quality management.

2. Research Overview

2.1. Research on quality management in education and vocational training

Myron Tribus Exergy, Inc. Hayward, CA (1992) with "Quality Management in Education" the author's view of quality management is another method of establishing people's efforts. The goal is to harmonize the efforts, approach the assigned task with enthusiasm, engage in improving the work performed. Quality management is about improving relationships between managers and people who actually do the work; Compare Traditional Management and Quality Management from Ed Baker, of the Ford Motor Company.

West-Burnham, John; Davies, Brent (1994), Quality Management as a Response to Educational Change, research indicates quality management approaches are applied in some cases as characteristic to change. Quality is determined according to customer needs, in the sense of fit for purpose. To achieve this through continuous improvement, managed through prevention and measurable. In the context of education, quality is comprehensive; emphasizing values, customers and continuous improvement; and use techniques for evaluation. Key areas of activity include mission, leadership, customer focus, and quality assurance.

Barlosky, Martin; Lawton, Stephen (1994) in Developing Quality Schools: A Handbook pointed to quality schools in Toronto, Canada, which offer a philosophy of quality and are designed to guide the development and implementation of quality-oriented educational programs. Quality Schools are committed to creating enhanced learning environments through purpose, in partnership with educational enterprises. Quality Schools emphasize organizational purpose, commitment to leadership, teamwork, learning process, customer and management through data.

CHENG, Yin Cheong (2001) in "Paradigm Shifts in Quality Improvement in Education: Three Waves for the Future", pointing to worldwide improvements in the quality of education experiencing three waves. The first wave, internal quality assurance, focuses on improvement and internal efficiency. The second wave, interface quality assurance i.e. quality assurance focuses on the interface between the educational institution and the community. Primarily identify and assess stakeholder satisfaction with educational services, including the educational process and outcomes. Therefore, quality assurance is to ensure educational services meet the needs of stakeholders and are accountable to the public. The third wave, future quality assurance, drives a paradigm shift in education quality assurance. Determined by the relevance of education to the future needs of individuals, communities and society.

Edward Sallis (2002), Total Quality Management in Education. The work was republished for the third time, the author studied the issues of quality, the origins of the quality movement, the contributions of Deming,

Shewhart and Juran on quality, the interest in quality development.... The author suggests that quality may be the only differentiating changing factor for an organization; analysis of two concepts of quality is absolute, the concept of relative quality; analysis of the customer's role in terms of quality; indicates the levels of quality management including quality control; comprehensive quality and quality assurance. The concepts of quality control, quality assurance; explain the differences of these two concepts. In particular, applying comprehensive quality management in education; develop a quality framework and analyze the components in the framework: leadership and strategy; systems and processes; teamwork; self-assessment.

Suzana Vlaši ć, Smiljana Vale, Danijela Križman Puhar (2009) with "Quality Management in Education" argues that "Quality management is a part of management that aims to achieve quality goals through quality planning, monitoring, assurance and improvement". Quality management involves everyone in the organization. The criteria relate to quality indicators to help schools identify important areas of activity. Quality education is a dynamic, multidimensional concept that relates not only to the educational model, but also to its mission, institutions and goals, as well as to the specific standards of the system, institution, program or event. In education, quality determination can compare the result with the set goal or compare it with previously established standards. The author argues that quality must be consciously managed to meet quality needs. With the concept of quality management is an integral part of management. Therefore, the role of management not only achieves goals, but also improves quality. To achieve this manage activities from setting policies, plans, and being implemented within the quality system, and at the same time having appropriate monitoring plans. To effectively manage an organization must have a quality management system. Quality management systems include, structure, processes, processes and other resources necessary for the application of quality management. A quality system that is inseparable from international and European quality standards. Since a standard is the formalization of the basic principles of quality management.

Douglas Matorera (2018) with "Quality Management Systems in Education", the study indicates and analyzes quality management systems consisting of three perspectives: quality, management and systems, the general focus of the QMS is the planning, directing, organizing, monitoring and control of the system or process of providing education. At the input stages, is the selection of inputs of the highest quality. At the process stages, is the correct combination and combination that will provide the highest quality consistent with the creation of the right and accurate outputs and results. At the output stages, are the output of products and services that satisfy and satisfy customers. The author argues that the path to high quality education should be designed from the vision of the organization, and the vision should be clearly definitive about the goals and quality indicators. aspects of educational management are: infrastructure management; quality control and quality assurance; management of resources/inputs; educational process; output management.

Domestic research on quality management in education

The research work of Nguyen Loc (2009) ed., Mac Van Trang, Nguyen Cong Giap in "Management rationale in educational institutions" researches and analyzes many management reasoning issues in educational institutions. Research indicates that management is the process of planning, organizing, leading, and examining the work of organizational members, and using the organization's available resources to achieve its goals. In-depth analysis of the nature of management; the functions of management and affirmation planning as a management and inspection function as well as a management function; planning guidelines; planning methods; types of planning of an organization, techniques and planning tools..., and many other issues related to management in the educational institution.

Author Nguyen Duc Chinh (2017) edited with "Quality Management in Education" introducing the history of research and development of quality management science; the concepts of quality, quality in education, quality of education from the perspective of quality management, college quality and vocational training; defines "quality management in education as the development and operation of a management system (on the basis of standards and criteria) aimed at influencing quality assurance conditions in all stages of the educational process,

for all products of the whole system, not on the quality of each stage or each product. singles"; analysis of levels in quality management; principles in the development and operation of a quality management system; the premise of building and operating a quality management system; introduce and analyze some quality management models and some typical quality assurance models such as EFQM, AUN, American quality assessment model, BS 5750 model ... In addition, the author also guides the development of a quality management system on the basis of a set of standards for evaluating the quality of educational institutions; guide the development of strategic plans to improve the quality of educational institutions. This is a new monograph, providing an overview and on quality management in education.

Research on quality management in vocational training

Fernando Vargas Zúñiga (2004), Quality management in vocational training, The use of standards and their different applications, shows that clients, employers in diverse markets, always require the best incentives and educational institutions must ensure quality. Quality management of educational institutions is related to the competitiveness of the organization. If the learning environment reflects conformity with standards, certain competencies of learners, this in relation to the quality of learners, can be developed. A vocational training institution that develops good practice, compliance with international standards will contribute to the development of learners' core skills. At the same time, organizations affirm external brands and will be certified for quality.

Martin Poda! and Roman. Hrmo (2013), Introduction of a Quality Management System for Vocational Education and Training in Slovakia, introduces the model of quality assessment of vocational education and training currently being implemented in many vocational schools in Western Slovakia and Austria. The objective of the study is to develop and apply an open, flexible and adaptable quality management system; introduce and guide how to evaluate each indicator such as: student results; the rate of use of methods in assessment, examination and classification; use teaching methods and styles; the quality of the material environment; partnerships and resources; the quality of the psycho-social environment; graduates continue their studies; graduates with jobs; analyzing the current state and applying existing quality management approaches and systems in vocational education and training; building a model for quality management of vocational education.

Michael Glykas, Omar Hasan Bailey, Mirvat Omar Al Maery, Nawaf Omar Al Maery (2015), Process and Quality Management in Vocational Education & Training (VET) research aimed at evaluating the concept of quality management in Vocational Education and Training (VET). The main term in the QMS is "customer", because it controls and promotes the development of the system. The purpose of a quality management system in an organization is to establish a common vision for everyone, set and organize goals, as well as guide and transmit organizations towards a culture of quality. QMS as a continuous cycle with customer requirements at the beginning and customer satisfaction as the end result. The QMS cycle consists of the following elements: management responsibilities; measurement, analysis and improvement; products; manage resources, customer requirements, results to meet customer satisfaction. Leadership plays a key role and management is a key driver throughout the stages of development, implementation and retention. In this cycle, the concepts of quality focus on customers, strategy, human resources, leadership, process...

Cedefop (2015), Supporting Internal Quality Management and Quality Culture (Handbook for VET providers), this is the first publication that the European Vocational Training Development Centre (Cedefop) sends to vocational education and training (VET) providers, to help VET facilities start or improve quality approaches. To improve the quality of education, for the benefit of VET providers as well as students and society at large. This handbook is intended to guide VET providers through the quality management process within the organisation; guidance on the application of the PDCA (plan-implementation-inspection/evaluation) cycle or quality cycle in management; what factors affect the quality inside, outside the organization; creating a culture

of quality in vocational education and training institutions; quality improvement; provide assessment tools, ... this is the fundamental approach to any quality management system (QMS) in education and training.

Author Nguyen Van Hung (2016), PhD thesis majoring in educational management with the topic: "Training management of vocational colleges according to quality assurance approach" builds the rationale of training management according to the approach to the Mekong Delta of vocational colleges; assessing the current state of EIA of vocational colleges in the North central and Central regions according to the approach to the Mekong Delta; access to the training process according to the CIPO model; proposing EIA solutions according to the approach of vocational colleges.

PhD thesis in Management and Management with the topic: "Quality management of training in information technology in colleges in Ho Chi Minh City according to TQM approach", by author Ngo Xuan Binh (2016) researching the theoretical basis of training quality management according to TQM approach; develop a theoretical framework for quality management of IT industry training according to the TQM approach; proposing a quality management system for IT training according to TQM approach at colleges in Ho Chi Minh City. HCM and propose implementation solutions to ensure and gradually improve the training quality of the IT discipline.

2.2. Research on quality assurance in vocational education and training

Cedefop (2009) with "Accreditation and Quality Assurance in Vocational Education and Training" argues that: Quality is always linked to specific policy, institutional or individual objectives to be achieved; indicate the results of research on quality assurance and accreditation of vocational education and training of some countries such as Sweden, Italy, Ireland and Germany; quality assurance framework (CQAF) as a European quality tool. CQAF is a circular model, which includes goal setting and strategic planning, measuring results according to predefined goals, and using results in management change and planning. CQAF has a similar structure and consists of the same steps as the PDCA cycle.

Cedefop (2011) in "Quality assurance in vocational education and training: The role of accrediting VET providers" set out the European Framework of Reference for Quality Assurance (EQARF) at the institution level and system level. The European Quality Assurance Reference Framework includes, the quality assurance and improvement cycle (planning, implementation, evaluation and review/revision) based on the selection of quality criteria. These indicators can be applied to quality management both at the system level and at the level of educational and training institutions. The aim is to support, maintain diversity in approaches, as a reference tool to help Member States promote and monitor the continuous improvement of their VET systems.

Cedefop (2011) with "Glossary Quality in education and training" gives: The term "quality assurance in education and training is activities related to planning, implementation, evaluation, reporting and quality improvement, carried out to ensure that education and training meet the quality requirements of the expected stakeholders"; The term "quality management is all the activities of management that define quality policies, objectives and responsibilities and implement them by quality planning, quality control and quality assurance in a quality system". Source: ISO, 1994; nine general principles for quality assurance in higher education and VET.

EQAVET Malta (2013) Implementing Quality Assurance in Vocational Education and Training (VET) Institutions, A Manual for VET Providers, points out that vocational education and training institutions in Malta have implemented European quality assurance tools such as: The quality cycle includes, planning, implementing, evaluating and reviewing and adjusting; Quality assurance systems in accordance with national and European standards, specifically Malta has developed a system of quality assurance indicators and implementation guidelines on the basis of European quality assurance accounting for (75%) and the remaining 25% of Malta. Quality indicators include: (1) Investment in teacher and teacher training; (2) Teacher and student involvement in QA; (3) Participation rates in VET programmes; (4) VET programme completion rates;

(5) Employment rates in VET programmes; (6) Use skills acquired in the workplace; (7) Mechanism for determining training needs in the labor market; (8) Plans used to promote better access to VET; (9) Self-assessment; (10) Transparency of the EIA system; (11) Partnerships.

Ethel E. Idialu, Ambrose Alli University, Nigeria (2013), *Ensuring Quality Assurance In Vocational Education*, analyzes the concept of quality assurance in vocational education, points out the parameters of quality assurance in vocational education such as: teacher quality, program accreditation, inspection, supervision and evaluation; Factors that hinder quality assurance; Factors that can ensure quality in vocational education.

K.K. Navaratnam and Rory O'Connor (1993), *Quality Assurance in Vocational Education: meeting the needs of the nineties*, show that vocational training as a process and way of ensuring quality in every aspect of the process. It is necessary to fulfill the ongoing commitment of management to successfully implement quality assurance in vocational education. Guidance on how to use the concept of quality assurance to improve vocational training standards. Meet the needs of stakeholders and drive innovation and improvement in vocational education through quality assurance.

Theresa I. Bevans-gonzales (2004) with "The strengths and weaknesses of ISO 9000 in vocational education" applying ISO 9000 to vocational education institutions in the United States, research at nine career and technical centers in Pennsylvania indicates the strengths of ISO 9000 in vocational education such as: Future benefits; improve leadership; improve efficiency; saving time and organization; link the center with other organizations and industries; quality team, and increased people engagement. Weaknesses of ISO 9000: it is difficult to apply ISO 9000 to education; time-consuming and paper-intensive; ISO 9000 is considered a temporary quality fad and will soon be forgotten; lack of information about ISO 9000 and its implementation in the field; there is no individual involvement in this process; difficulty understanding the language and the terms of the standards.

Suzanne Gatt (2013), *The EQAVET experience in Malta: using similar indicators for different sectors and size of VET providers*, the study found that all vocational education and training institutions in Malta used similar quality assurance indicators in Malta self-indicators in European vocational education and training quality assurance and quality assurance indicators are implemented in all stages of the European quality cycle such as: planning, implementation, evaluation and review, adjustment. At the same time, point out the challenge of quality assurance requirements and support training institutions in their implementation to ensure quality.

Margareta Nikolovska (2014) with "Quality Approach in Vocational Education and Training in South Eastern Europe and Turkey: Building on the Torino Process Findings," in *Quality Assurance in Vocational Education and Training*, A collection for articles by ETF (2014), which delves into planning, implementation, evaluation and review; provide four quality assurance elements: (1) Establish clear, relevant and measurable common objectives and specific objectives of policies, processes, tasks and human resources; (2) Establish processes to ensure the achievement of common goals and specific objectives (e.g., partnership development, stakeholder engagement, resource allocation, and organizational and operational procedures); (3) Design mechanisms for evaluating achievements and outcomes by collecting and processing data to generate evaluation information; (4) Develop processes to achieve the results of new goals or objectives. The author suggests that quality management is accessible in a variety of ways.

Zeljko Raicevic and Margareta Nikolovska (2014) in "Quality Assurance in Vocational Education and Training: The Experience of Montenegro", A collection for articles by ETF (2014), pointed to the results of vocational education and training (VET) reforms in Montenegro based on the VET system. VET facilities in Montenegro, are divided into three categories: highly specialized areas; diverse programs; mixed facilities offering both general education and VET. The policy framework for improving internal quality (QI) in VET includes: external assessment and internal assessment. Montenegro's experience of assessment in the education system includes self-assessment, internal assessment of schools, preparation of internal assessment reports, external

assessment processes and external assessment team reports. Internal audits drive VET facilities to become more involved in QI activities, developing quality improvement plans. VET includes not only skills and professional knowledge, but also provides access to higher education, access to the labour market, and good opportunities for personal development and social integration.

Elizabeth Watters (2015) with her research "Promoting Quality Assurance in Vocational Education and Training the ETF Approach", quality management is the result of the systematic use of policies, methods and tools in a coordinated way to direct citizens and organizations towards achieving goals. predetermined quality. Therefore, it depends on people, individually and collectively, to perform work tasks in a quality-oriented way. Quality assurance is a comprehensive system that covers all stages of the quality cycle (planning, implementation, inspection, evaluation) and addresses context, inputs, processes, outputs and outcomes and is systematic with a top-down approach. The purpose of quality assurance in VET is to support processes and procedures that ensure good VET. The ETF approach to promoting VET quality assurance development, prioritizing continuous improvement of core measures, quality assurance for VET in relation to context and standards of inputs, processes, outputs and outcomes. At the same time, in relation to changing economies and labour markets and the growing need to support lifelong learning, and the internationalisation of VET may require a new approach to quality assurance. The ten key elements that make up the foundation of ETF access to drive quality assurance in VET reform are vision, strategy, leadership, collaboration, inquiry, planning, testing, improvement, vision and thinking.

World Health Organization (2008) with "Quality Assurance and Accreditation of Nursing and Midwifery Educational Institutions" focuses on four important issues: institutional experience in improving the quality of nursing and midwifery education; the concepts and frameworks of quality assurance and accreditation; draft guidelines on NMEI accreditation and quality assurance; and the role of educational institutions, regulatory bodies and national authorities in improving the quality of nursing and midwifery education. Quality is subjective and based on personal backgrounds, views and standards. It's everyone who desires or desires quality. Quality Assurance (QA) is one of the mechanisms developed by educational institutions to ensure that graduates achieve adequate educational and training standards. It can include internal and external QA. Internal QA refers to audits and assessments performed by a team inside the organization. External QA refers to audits and assessments conducted by a team from outside the organization, with the aim of making the audit more objective. Tools are required for auditing and evaluation. Guidelines for quality assurance of nursing and midwifery educational institutions.

Cecilia Latrach, Naldy Febré and Ingrid Demandes (2012) with "Quality Assurance in the Career of Nursing" analyzes the fundamentals of the concept of quality assurance of higher education in nursing. Given that quality assurance is a combination of planned and systematic actions necessary to provide appropriate reliability for a product or service that meets quality requirements. Quality assurance is based on the implementation of a system of work documents, establishing clear, fixed and objective rules that cover all aspects related to the operational process. This process begins with the design, planning, production, presentation, distribution, statistical techniques of control and training of employees. Quality assurance is a continuous, systematic and ongoing assessment, analysis and evaluation of the level of compliance with standards set at the local, national and international levels. Standards and indicators for quality management for nursing schools and the development of accreditation systems of nursing schools.

Maria Emília Galvão (2014) with "Making The Case for Vocational Education and Training Improvement: Issues and Challenges", in Quality Assurance in Vocational Education and Training, A collection for articles, ETF (2014), pointed to the results of the study of quality assurance (QA) and quality improvement (QI) issues and challenges of vocational education and training (VET). QA and QI are important issues in VET; the challenges to improving VET; core QA functions such as: identifying, measuring and improving quality; approach QA and QI in VET, given that the PDCA cycle, as a model that countries can use to create (or modify), one of the most popular models of QI; key factors for improving and ensuring VET quality such as

improving VET teaching and training processes and learning outcomes; accountability; monitoring and evaluation. Countries must have a quality vision and policy with clear definitions of quality and QA approaches.

Maria Emília Galvão, VET providers' self-monitoring by using the EQAVET toolbox of indicators, VET providers self-monitoring using the EQAVET indicators in a four-step cycle and guides the implementation and analysis of these steps. Step 1: Organise the supplier self-monitoring process by focusing on the objectives of VET delivery and by using EQAVET indicators; Step 2: Implement the self-regulatory plan through guiding questions and apply EQAVET indicators; Step 3: Collect and analyze data and turn it into information through reflection of the relevant edges; Step 4: Turn information into evidence by evaluating, making decisions, setting priorities, and taking action to change.

Roman Hrmo, Juraj Mi! Tina, Lucia Kri! Tofiaková (2016) with "Improving the Quality of Technical and Vocational Education in Slovakia for European Labour Market Needs", a study of the education system of technical and vocational secondary schools in Slovakia, in training a qualified workforce for local and global labor markets; introducing and developing the project "Model for improving the quality of graduates and job applicants in the European labor market". Aims to develop a model for improving the quality of graduates and job applicants in the European labor market. Therefore, the study focused on graduates of vocational secondary schools in Slovakia and improving their main competencies. Quality assurance in Slovakia plays a decisive role in modernizing education and training systems and improving their performance and operational capabilities.

Andrea Bateman and Mike Coles (2017), Towards Quality Assurance of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) have shown qualification quality assurance in TVET in 13 Asia-Pacific countries; the TVET system of each country; quality assurance; reviews; strengths and weaknesses of TVET quality; opportunities and barriers to improve the current quality assurance process and proposals to improve qualification quality assurance.

Andrea BHRan and Mike Coles (2017), Guidelines for the Quality Assurance of TVET Qualifications in the Asia-Pacific Region conducted by researchers and representatives of many countries in Asia Pacific.

3. Conclusions

Through the overview of the above-mentioned research works, some comments can be drawn as follows:

Research on CLGD is conducted at various levels in education and at various levels. However, the research works have given the author an overview of CL, PMC, PMC, PMC, PMC in vocational education and training, DBCL, DBCL in vocational education and training, access to EIA in vocational education and training, quality management system and issues related to quality assurance in vocational education and training; research directions in quality assurance approaches to clarify the core content of the topic. Thereby, the system author has a rationale, a way to assess the situation, thereby proposing solutions and guiding the implementation of quality management of medical colleges according to the European approach to quality assurance of vocational education and training (EQAVET);

Through the research works, the author realizes that currently, there is no research on school quality management, specifically the Medical College following the European approach to quality assurance of vocational education and training (EQAVET). With the aim of ensuring and improving the quality of schools and aiming to meet the needs of the international labor market in the current context.

Facing that practice, for universities to ensure and improve quality and aim to meet the needs of the international labor market in the current context is very necessary and poses challenges for Vietnamese Medical Colleges. Therefore, the author continues to inherit the above scientific research works, to continue researching and proposing solutions to manage the quality of medical colleges according to the European approach to quality assurance of vocational education and training (EQAVET), which will ensure and improve the quality of schools and aim to meet domestic workers. but also supply to countries around the world.

General Assessment

On the basis of the overview study, the author makes some comments on the issues that have not been covered by the study as follows:

Firstly, the overview of the above research works gives the author a comprehensive view of vocational education and training but in many different approaches: There are research works on higher education management in Hungary; there are research works on training quality management at private universities in the direction of approaching AUN - QA; there are research works on management of training quality at private universities in the direction of AUN - QA; there are research works on management of training quality at private universities in the direction of AUN - QA; quality management of training at Thai Binh University in the direction of quality assurance approach; have research works on training quality management of vocational colleges according to cipo quality assurance approach; have research works on training quality management at intermediate schools according to ISO and TQM approaches; have research works on quality management of training in information technology of vocational colleges according to TQM approach; Most of the research works on training quality management at universities and colleges. However, there have been no research works on the university's management, especially the Medical College under the European Approach to Vocational Education and Training (EQAVET). Therefore, the author continues to study the management of the Medical College according to the approach of European Vocational Education and Training (EQAVET) in a methodical and systematic way.

Secondly, research works on management management in education have proposed many different models and methods of management for the purpose of improving the EQAVET of educational institutions. to ensure and improve the quality of schools and aim to meet the needs of the international labor market in the current context. This is a new direction that needs to be further researched and applied in all medical colleges throughout Vietnam in the context of international integration.

Third, the above studies propose many different solutions. The author of the study and analysis in the direction of quality management of the University according to the european approach to quality assurance of vocational education and training (EQAVET), is proposing 11 quality assurance indicators to evaluate the quality of the school on the basis of vietnameseization of 10 quality assurance indicators of Europe to match the practice of Vietnamese Health Colleges Male; apply the internal quality assurance system and quality assurance cycle to implement school quality management at Vietnam Medical Colleges. This is a problem that differs from other studies. This is also a completely new approach that the author will continue to research and propose solutions, guiding the implementation of quality management of medical colleges according to the European approach to quality assurance of vocational education and training (EQAVET), to ensure and improve the quality of schools and aim to meet the needs of the international labor market in the current context.

Issues that need further study

With the above-mentioned analysis and overview studies, the university's management team follows the European approach to quality assurance of vocational education and training (EQAVET), in the coming time it is necessary to solve the following issues:

It is necessary to further clarify the rationale for quality management of medical colleges in accordance with the European approach to quality assurance of vocational education and training (EQAVET).

Firstly, in the context of deep international integration, this issue has posed vietnam's vocational education and training with many opportunities but also challenges. This shows that universities are aiming for quality assurance in accordance with the European vocational education and training quality assurance (EQAVET) approach, in order to ensure and improve the quality of schools and thereby train quality medical human resources to meet the needs of the international labor market in the current context. With this goal, the

role of quality assurance is extremely important, is an essential element of schools to ensure and improve the quality of schools. To ensure and improve the quality of schools, quality management is considered one of the effective methods. Research on quality assurance approach in quality management the University will contribute to ensuring and improving the quality of schools aiming to meet the needs of the international labor market. At the time of the study, there were no medical colleges in Vietnam, implementing quality management according to the Approach of the European Vocational Education and Training Quality Assurance Framework (EQAVET) to implement school quality management. nor has it been mentioned in any of the studies. This issue needs to be studied methodically and systematically.

Secondly, the author will continue to study the experience of the School management in the country and in the world to continue inheriting, consolidating and developing the theoretical and practical basis of the Medical College's management solutions according to the approach to quality assurance of European vocational education and training (EQAVET). Future research will continue to study some models of management management in some countries around the world and in Vietnam to flexibly apply in research works, suitable for the context of international integration.

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